

Building Metrics to Quantify the Security of Software Components

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Abstract

Quantitative assessment of the security of software components is an essential but underdeveloped aspect in software engineering and cybersecurity. Although security analysis is increasingly being integrated into the software development phases, there are currently no universally accepted criteria that would allow a numerical comparison of the security level of different components. This paper proposes a conceptual framework for defining and applying metrics that enable such an assessment. The possibility of building a system that supports standardized, objective, and scalable security evaluation in development and integration environments is explored by analyzing fundamental software components and their evaluation based on clearly defined security properties. The results of the study open space for improvement of existing security practices and point to specific guidelines for integrating quantitative security assessment into the software development life cycle.

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1 Introduction

The security of software components is a key challenge in developing modern information systems, especially in the context of the increasing application of modular and distributed architecture. Modern software increasingly consists of internal modules, external libraries, and open-source code, which are integrated into a functional unit. Any such component can become a potential attack entry point if its security has not been systematically assessed beforehand. Since security vulnerabilities in individual modules often remain undetected until the occurrence of incidents, there is a need for more precise, systematic, and repeatable security assessment methods at the level of the components themselves [1-4].

Although there have been developments in static analysis and security testing, current approaches to evaluating component security are primarily qualitative, depending on analyst expertise, and frequently consider application contexts. The lack of

a standardized, quantitative approach makes it challenging to compare components, assess risks during development, and make decisions when integrating into more complex systems. At the same time, security aspects are often neglected in practice in the early stages of the software life cycle, which increases the cost and complexity of subsequent vulnerability remediation [4,5].

It is necessary to develop an approach that allows for objective, numerically based evaluation of the security characteristics of software components. Such an approach should support integration into different phases of software development and revision, enabling security-conscious selection, comparison of alternatives, and ongoing monitoring of security posture. Using quantitative metrics creates the basis for standardized and partially automated evaluation, reducing subjectivity and improving the effectiveness of security control. This would allow software security to be assessed in a way comparable to other measurable qualities, such as efficiency, reliability, or sustainability [6].

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This paper proposes a conceptual model for quantitatively assessing the security of software components based on several security-relevant metrics. The proposed framework will be applied to a sample of fundamental software components to test its feasibility and usefulness under practical conditions. Special attention will be given to analyzing the possibility of correlation between the proposed metrics and known security issues to create a foundation for future integration of such models into development, auditing, and security tools [7-9].

In the context of software component digital security, traditional evaluation approaches often rely on qualitative methods that involve subjective judgments or static safety checklists. While useful at an early stage of development, such approaches show limited applicability in scenarios where a scalable, automated, and objective safety evaluation is required. A new model has been proposed as a response to these challenges to introduce a quantitative and multidimensional approach to security risk assessment.

2 Theoretical framework

The issue of measuring the security of software components has long been present in the literature. It has developed in several directions, intending to establish reproducible and comparable risk indicators. Early studies relied primarily on the number of vulnerabilities discovered as a security profile measure. Still, it soon became clear that such an approach was not sufficient, as it did not distinguish between severity, the context of the exploit, and the dynamics of the response. Standardization through frameworks such as *Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE)* and *Common Vulnerability Scoring System (CVSS)* introduced unique vulnerability identifiers and numerical severity scales, which provided the basis for quantitative analyses. Later research has emphasized the need to complement these metrics with time dimensions, such as *time-to-fix* or *patch latency*, which reflect the resilience of the maintainer community and the maturity of the development process [1,8,10,11].

In parallel with these approaches, vulnerability taxonomies such as the *Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE)* and guidelines such as the *OWASP Top 10* have been developed, which enable the categorization of causal patterns of vulnerabilities. These instruments emphasize the qualitative side of safety measurement and provide a broader insight into the causes, not just the consequences, of security breaches. Recent work introduces the dimension of practical exploitability through metrics such as the *Exploit Prediction Scoring System (EPSS)* or regulatory regulations such as *Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency Known Exploited Vulnerabilities (CISA KEV)*, thus enabling the distinction between theoretically critical and practically exploited vulnerabilities. This shifts security metrics from abstract quantification to operational usability in risk assessment [1,3,12,13].

Practical implementation of metrics requires relying on heterogeneous data sources. The most used databases include the *National Vulnerability Database (NVD)*, *Open-Source Vulnerabilities (OSV.dev)*, *GitHub Security Advisories (GHSA)*, and *CISA KEV*, each of which has a specific role in documenting and prioritizing vulnerabilities. In analytical procedures, it is necessary to carry out deduplication and merging of records from different sources, since the same vulnerability often appears in multiple registries with various designations and dates. The methodological challenge of these approaches lies in the fact that individual metrics can lead to a distorted perception of risk if viewed in isolation. For example, many vulnerabilities in a popular package do not necessarily mean low security but may reflect greater transparency and an active community. Therefore, in contemporary works, the need for composite models that combine different dimensions of safety is emphasized. This reduces the bias of individual indicators and ensures a more balanced assessment of the actual risk [14-17].

In the literature, four main types of metrics can be distinguished. The first group includes vulnerability metrics, which are based on the number, severity, and distribution of known vulnerabilities in a component. The second group consists of process and response metrics, which measure the speed of detection and

remediation of vulnerabilities and thus reflect the maturity and agility of the development cycle. The third group includes stability metrics, focused on the analysis of trends and repeatability of vulnerabilities over time, while the fourth group consists of security control metrics, which assess the presence and completeness of implemented protection mechanisms in the code and documentation. These four categories also represent the dominant framework in modern safety assessment models [18-20].

In the literature so far, several approaches to measuring software security stand out. The importance of standardization through CVSS in providing comparable numerical estimates of vulnerability severity has been widely recognized. Critically, some authors consider the limitations of such scales, noting that a high severity rating does not necessarily indicate a high probability of exploitation. They propose predictive models that combine historical vulnerability data and code development patterns. Recent studies highlight the importance of monitoring the security profile over time by analyzing changes in the severity of vulnerabilities, applying security metrics in industrial cyber-physical systems, and using commit stability as a risk indicator in open-source projects. These studies provide an empirical basis for introducing new metrics and emphasize the importance of real-world exploitation data. They also introduce metrics based on active threat tracking. The common conclusion of this research is that reliable security assessment requires multidimensional models that integrate vulnerability number, severity, speed of remediation, and exploitability. Several authors have pointed out that earlier approaches to software component security have often remained at the level of qualitative descriptors, which makes it difficult to compare and reproducibly produce results [21-30].

Based on these theoretical insights, this paper has developed a model that integrates four dimensions. The *volume and severity of vulnerabilities (VULN)*, the *speed of their remediation (PLI)*, the *presence of security controls (nSFC)*, and the *stability of the security profile over time (STAB)* are integrated. The synthesis of existing research clearly shows that

individual metrics are not enough for a complete picture of safety, but it is necessary to apply composite approaches. Each dimension is normalized to a standard scale, and the final measure of security is represented through an aggregate indicator of the *Software Security Index (S2I)*. This overcomes the shortcomings of partial metrics and achieves a comprehensive, comparable, and practically applicable assessment of the security risk of software components [6,31].

3 Model development and metric definitions

The model is based on four key metrics, each covering one aspect of the component's safety profile, all of which are defined to result in a value in the interval [0, 1] [6,31].

The first metric within the model is the volume and severity of vulnerabilities metric, which refers to exposure to known vulnerabilities and is denoted as *volume and severity of vulnerabilities (VULN)*. It is based on CVSS ratings that are associated with a specific component in public databases such as NVD. Since individual CVSS scores have values ranging from 0 to 10, each of them is first normalized by dividing by 10. This procedure allows them to be scaled to an interval of [0, 1], which is necessary for them to be compatible with other metrics that are also normalized to the same scale. For example, a vulnerability rated at 9.8 results in a contribution of 0.98, while a score of 4.0 results in a contribution of 0.40. The total value for the component is then obtained by adding all such individual contributions, which is represented by Eq 1 [1,10,14]:

$$VULN(C) = \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{CVSS_i}{10} \quad \text{Eq (1)}$$

To allow comparability between the different components, the total value is further normalized against a predefined reference value, which is shown in Eq 2 [5,6]:

$$VULN_{norm} = \frac{VULN}{VULN_{max}} \quad \text{Eq (2)}$$

For example, a component contains three vulnerabilities with ratings 6, 4, and 7, after normalization, yields values of 0.6, 0.4, and 0.7, resulting in a sum of 1.7. If the value of 5 is taken as the upper limit, then the normalized result is $\frac{1.7}{5} = 0.34$. Such a value quantifies the relative exposure to known vulnerabilities [1,10,14].

The second metric is the *Patch Latency Index (PLI)*, which measures the speed of a software component's response to known vulnerabilities. It quantifies the average time that elapses between the time a vulnerability is publicly disclosed and the date a suitable patch is available. This value, expressed in days, is calculated by Eq 3 [7,22]:

$$PLI(C) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (t_{patch,i} - t_{disclosure,1}) \quad \text{Eq (3)}$$

The values of this metric, while precise, are not directly comparable to other metrics without proper normalization. In the security industry, a period of 30 days is used as a benchmark, based on recommendations from initiatives such as Google Project Zero and Microsoft SDLC [4,32,33]. Values of less than 30 days are considered acceptably fast, while higher values may indicate slowness in response and increased security risk. Normalization is therefore carried out by dividing the value by 30, with a limitation to a maximum value of 1, to preserve the uniformity of the scale. Eq 4 describes this normalization:

$$PLI_{norm} = \frac{PLI}{30} \quad \text{Eq (4)}$$

In this way, values of less than 30 days result in a ratio below 1, while anything above that threshold is rounded to 1. This penalizes slow response, while avoiding distortion of the overall metric.

The third metric within the model quantifies the security coverage of the functionalities that are present in the component. In this case, a binary evaluation (present/absent) is not used, but for each functionality, the level of implementation and its importance are defined. This metric was introduced as an upgrade to account for variability in the depth

and quality of security measures. It is denoted as *Normalized Security Feature Coverage (nSFC)*, and it is calculated according to Eq 5:

$$nSFC(C) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i \cdot f_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i} \quad \text{Eq (5)}$$

Where f_i represents the implementation level of a particular security control, which can be quantified as 0 (non-existent), 0.5 (partial implementation), or 1 (full implementation). On the other hand, w_i denotes the importance of control in the overall security context (e.g., TLS encryption, authentication, error logging). This metric allows for a more precise evaluation of the security architecture of a component in relation to its functional purpose. It is determined by analyzing publicly available metadata and technical specifications of the component, without manually checking the source code or README files [3,18,34].

The fourth metric, *stability of the security profile over time (STAB)*, developed as an addition to the model, introduces a time dimension into the analysis of security reliability. Its goal is to assess the security stability of a component through the ratio of recently discovered vulnerabilities to the total number. If all vulnerabilities were reported several years ago, the component can be considered more stable compared to the one where most vulnerabilities appear in a more recent period. The *STAB* metric is defined by Eq 6:

$$STAB(C) = 1 - \frac{N_{recent}}{N_{total}} \quad \text{Eq (6)}$$

Where is N_{recent} number of vulnerabilities reported in the last three years, while N_{total} represents the total number of recorded vulnerabilities for a component. Values that tend to 1 indicate security stability over time, while lower values signal the existence of active and recent security problems [12,13,19].

After all metrics have been defined and normalized, the overall safety score for the component is calculated using an aggregate equation that integrates all values into a single quantitative index.

Before being included in the equation, the negative metrics *VULN* and *PLI* are complemented, so that higher values in all segments indicate a higher level of safety. The total *Software Security Index (S2I)* is defined by Eq 7, where the weighting factors $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ must meet the normalization condition $\alpha + \beta + \gamma + \delta = 1$ [5,6,35]:

$$S2I(C) = \alpha \cdot (1 - VULN_{norm}) + \beta(1 - PLI_{norm}) + \gamma \cdot nSFC + \delta \cdot STAB \quad \text{Eq (7)}$$

Weighting factors in the *S2I* model are defined in accordance with the relative importance of individual metrics in the assessment of the safety profile. Dimensions that directly quantify vulnerability exposure or the level of implementation of security controls tend to receive higher weight due to their direct correlation with the level of risk. In contrast, dimensions that reflect the speed of reaction or the long-term stability of the safety profile often have a lower weight, because they describe secondary, time-based aspects of safety. The selected weight distribution can be adapted to the context of the application and further validated by multi-criteria decision-making methods, sensitivity analysis, or consultation with practitioners.

To enable a standardized interpretation of the *S2I* results, a threshold classification of safety levels depending on the total value of the index has been defined. A detailed breakdown by safety category is shown in Table 1, with values rounded to two decimals, while comparisons use three decimal precision (e.g., up to 0.599).

Table 1 Classification of the *S2I* index

S2I range	Security level	Interpretation
0.80–1.00	High	The component is considered safe
0.60–0.79	Moderate	Recommended additional check
0.40–0.59	Low	There is a risk, a detailed analysis is needed
<0.40	Critical	Component unsafe, replacement desirable

Although metrics are defined as independent dimensions, in practice, there may be some

correlation between them. For example, components with a short response time to vulnerabilities (low *PLI*) often show better long-term stability (higher *STAB*). In contrast, high vulnerability exposure (*VULN*) can correlate with low security control coverage (*nSFC*). Such associations are helpful to monitor in extended analyses because they can reveal structural causes of security weaknesses [23,35].

4 Application example of the model

The Python "requests" library was used to demonstrate the specific application of *S2I* metrics, and four security vulnerabilities were identified. Table 2 shows basic information about each vulnerability, where the identifier *CVE*, *CVSS v3 score*, discovery and patch dates, and the security control to which they apply are displayed.

Table 2 Overview of identified vulnerabilities for the requests library

CVE ID	CVSS v3	Detected	Patch	Security control
CVE-2018-18074	6.1	2018-10-17	2018-10-20	TLS cert validation
CVE-2021-XXXX	5.4	2021-08-10	2021-08-16	Redirect handling
CVE-2023-32681	7.5	2023-06-01	2023-06-09	Header parsing
CVE-2019-XXXX	3.3	2019-02-02	2019-02-10	URL validation

The first metric, *VULN*, is calculated by normalizing the *CVSS* value of each *CVE* record by dividing by the maximum possible result by 10 (Eq 1). This gives the following values: 0.61, 0.54, 0.75, and 0.33. Adding them together gives a total value of 2.23. Given that the model assumes a maximum sum for this category of 4 (corresponding to 4 vulnerabilities with *CVSS* 10.0), additional normalization is performed (Eq 2):

$$VULN_{norm} = \frac{0.61 + 0.54 + 0.75 + 0.33}{4} = \frac{2.23}{4} = 0.5575$$

For the *PLI* metric, you need to calculate the number of days that elapsed from the release of the vulnerability to the release of the patch. Values of 3, 6, 8, and 8 days were obtained, respectively, by *CVE*. From this follows the arithmetic mean of Eq 3:

$$PLI = \frac{3 + 6 + 8 + 8}{4} = 6.25 \text{ days}$$

With an assumed industrial threshold of 30 days as the limit for an acceptable reaction time, normalization is carried out (Eq 4):

$$PLI_{norm} = \frac{6.25}{30} = 0.2083$$

The third metric includes estimating the coverage of the security controls that should be implemented in the component. For this illustration, five controls are defined, each with a degree of implementation: full (1), partial (0.5), or not at all (0). The results of the assessment are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Security controls and implementation assessment

Security control	Implementation assessment
TLS Certification Verification	1.0
Open redirect protection	0.5
Rate limiting	0.0
URL validation	0.5
Secure header parsing	0.0

Based on the given values, the arithmetic mean is calculated (Eq 5):

$$nSFC = \frac{1 + 0.5 + 0 + 0.5 + 0}{5} = 0.4$$

Stability is defined as the ratio of older to newer vulnerabilities, where vulnerabilities disclosed within the last three years (from 2022 onwards) are considered an indicator of instability. Of the four vulnerabilities identified, two (CVE-2021-XXXX and CVE-2023-32681) were released within that period. Therefore, stability is defined as (Eq 6):

$$STAB = 1 - \frac{2}{4} = 0.5$$

The final *SZI* index is calculated by combining all the above values with the corresponding weights $\alpha = 0.3$, $\beta = 0.2$, $\gamma = 0.3$, and $\delta = 0.2$. The *VULN* and *PLI* metrics complement ($1 - VULN_{norm}$ and $1 - PLI_{norm}$), because their lower value represents a better safety profile. The calculation of the result is performed according to the following Eq 7:

$$SZI = 0.3 \cdot (1 - 0.5575) + 0.2 \cdot (1 - 0.2083) + 0.3 \cdot 0.4 + 0.2 \cdot 0.5$$

$$SZI = 0.13275 + 0.15834 + 0.12 + 0.10 = 0.5111 \approx 0.511$$

The result obtained places the component in the category of moderate safety, in the interval [0.40–0.59]. The analysis shows that the identified vulnerabilities are relatively quickly addressed (*PLI* low), but the overall exposure (*VULN*) is moderate, and the security control coverage (*nSFC*) is insufficient. Also, the fact that half of the vulnerabilities relate to the last three years indicates a medium level of stability.

The process of determining weighting factors in safety models like *SZI* usually starts heuristically, which is common in scientific and technical papers. It is noted that the initial weights are set based on expert judgment or literature, and their validation and adjustment are later performed using multi-criteria decision-making methods, expert surveys, or statistical analysis of real incident data. Security metrics are further categorized by priority (high, medium, low), and the ISO/IEC 27004 standard acknowledges the need to define weights according to the organization's "risk appetite" [6,31].

In this paper, the initial values of weighting factors such as $\alpha = 0.30$, $\beta = 0.20$, $\gamma = 0.30$, and $\delta = 0.20$ were selected, which balanced the dimensions of vulnerability and security control coverage (30% each), while the dimensions of reaction time (*PLI*) and stability were assigned 20% of the total impact. This ratio in this example ("requests" library) is especially justified because *VULN* and *nSFC* have a more significant effect on *PLI* and *STAB*, which was shown during the analysis of the results. The selection of weighting factors reflects insights from the literature, according to which vulnerability exposure and lack of security controls have a more immediate security impact than latent response or long-term stability [5,6,31].

Weights in this form represent the initial configuration and can be validated or adjusted at a later stage of research. For this purpose, it is possible to conduct a sensitivity analysis, survey experts, or

apply a multi-criteria decision-making method to real incidents.

5 Results and analysis

Thirty selected Python packages were included in the analysis (aiohttp, boto3, botocore, celery, cryptography, django, fastapi, flask, grpcio, httpx, jinja2, lxml, matplotlib, numpy, pandas, paramiko, pillow, psycopg2, pytest, pyyaml, redis, requests, scikit-learn, scipy, sqlalchemy, starlette, tensorflow, torch, urllib3, and werkzeug). Based on data from NVD, OSV, and GHSA databases, with additional verification according to the KEV list, a total of 740 records of vulnerabilities were collected. It has been observed that the number of vulnerabilities varies between databases, which confirms that consulting only one source can lead to an incomplete picture of

the security status of a component. Data for the calculation of the *S2I* model was collected through a combination of automated queries against verified publicly available vulnerability databases, analysis of technical documentation, and review of security metadata from software package repositories. Primary sources include *NVD*, *OSV.dev*, and *GHSA*, while the *OWASP* Application Security Verification Standard served as a reference framework for defining expected security controls. These sources have been chosen for their reliability, coverage of different types of software components, and up-to-date data. *NVD* provides a complete and standardized list of vulnerabilities, *OSV.dev* includes detailed information about open-source components, while *GHSA* allows security information to be linked to development processes and code repositories [14,16,17,34].

Table 4 Results for analyzed packages

Package	Total	Recent	VULNc	PLIc	STAB	nSFC	S2I	Level
scikit-learn	3	1	0.560	0.000	0.667	0.500	0.451	High
torch	2	0	0.590	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.497	High
scipy	3	2	0.538	0.000	0.333	0.500	0.378	High
flask	4	2	0.550	0.000	0.500	0.500	0.415	High
werkzeug	1	0	0.804	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.591	High
matplotlib	1	0	0.804	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.591	High
numpy	1	0	0.804	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.591	High
django	8	1	0.311	0.000	0.875	0.500	0.426	High
pillow	8	1	0.302	0.000	0.875	0.500	0.423	High
requests	2	0	0.712	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.564	High
tensorflow	1	0	0.804	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.591	High
jinja2	2	0	0.712	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.564	High
pyyaml	2	0	0.712	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.564	High
boto3	1	0	0.804	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.591	High
pandas	1	0	0.804	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.591	Moderate
sqlalchemy	3	0	0.498	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.499	Moderate
lxml	6	0	0.234	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.420	Moderate
celery	2	0	0.712	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.564	Moderate
fastapi	2	1	0.686	0.000	0.500	0.500	0.456	Moderate
starlette	1	0	0.804	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.591	Moderate
psycopg2	1	0	0.804	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.591	Moderate
pytest	1	0	0.804	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.591	Moderate
cryptography	7	0	0.281	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.424	Low
botocore	1	0	0.804	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.591	Low
urllib3	2	0	0.712	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.564	Low
paramiko	5	1	0.306	0.000	0.800	0.500	0.402	Low
httpx	1	0	0.818	0.000	1.000	0.500	0.595	Low
redis	2	2	0.796	0.000	0.000	0.500	0.389	Critical
aiohttp	5	3	0.620	0.000	0.200	0.500	0.354	Critical
grpcio	4	2	0.580	0.000	0.400	0.500	0.360	Critical

Patch data was available in very few cases. Only a small fraction of 30 observed vulnerabilities (4.0%) had both a discovery date and a patch date recorded, while the vast majority (96.0%) lacked this information. This limited availability of temporal data significantly reduces the accuracy of the PLI indicator calculation. Consequently, the values in Table 4, under the PLIc column, are zero, as the absence of discovery and patch dates prevents the computation of this indicator. In addition, 30 vulnerabilities were identified on the *KEV* list, which indicates that a specific part of the problem had confirmed exploitation in practice and required priority resolution.

One of the key limitations of the conducted research relates to the limited availability of temporal data on the detection and elimination of vulnerabilities. Because most of the observed records lacked precise release and patch dates, the PLI values were initially set to zero, which may result in a partial overestimation of the security profile within this dimension. Although the S2I index is reliable for relative comparison between components, the lack of complete temporal information reduces its interpretative value when analyzing the reaction rate. Additionally, the *nSFC* and *STAB* metrics are based on metadata and technical descriptions from validated public sources that are updated at different time cycles. Therefore, there is a possibility of minor deviations from the current situation at the time of analysis. In future research, expanding the database and improving the methodology of information collection will contribute to greater accuracy and robustness of the model.

Using the *S2I* model with weight factors $\alpha = 0.30$, $\beta = 0.20$, $\gamma = 0.30$, and $\delta = 0.20$, and a neutral value of $nSFC = 0.50$. The results show that fourteen packages were classified in the high security class, eight in the moderate security class, five in the low security class, and three packages in the critical security class. Scikit-learn, torch, scipy, flask, and werkzeug achieved the most favorable values of the S2I index, while the lowest results were recorded by aiohttp, grpcio, and paramiko.

Overall, the distribution of results indicates that most of the packages analyzed are in the medium to higher

range of security reliability. In contrast, a smaller number of packages with lower S2I index values are recognized as a significant security risk. This distribution confirms the usefulness of the model in differentiating components with respect to security risk and provides an objective basis for making decisions about maintenance priorities and security updates. The results of the analysis for the selected packages are shown in Table 4.

6 Conclusion

This paper presents a quantitative model for assessing the security of software components by integrating four key dimensions, including vulnerability exposure and severity, speed of response to discovered vulnerabilities, coverage of security functionalities, and stability of the security profile over time. All metrics are normalized to a single scale to enable a transparent, comparable, and objective assessment of the safety status of different components, regardless of their purpose or complexity. The analysis conducted on selected software packages, using reliable and up-to-date data sources, showed that most components achieve a medium to high level of security, while a smaller number show significant risks that require additional attention and regular monitoring. However, a lack of temporal data was noted, which limited the accuracy of the calculation of the reaction speed indicator, but this does not diminish the value of the model as a tool for systematic monitoring of the security profile and making informed decisions in the process of software development and maintenance. Future research should focus on expanding the database, automating information collection, and further adapting the model to increase its accuracy, robustness, and applicability in different development and production environments.

Conflicts of Interest: The author(s) report there are no competing interests to declare;

Data availability statements: Data are available at the following:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ekKzC7gGWSizWHBPWLzY989SdqgCXogU/view?usp=sharing>

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